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The Role of Traditional Institutions in Conflict Resolution and their Impact on Grassroots Development: A Study of Selected Communities in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Traditional institutions are vital for the sustainability of the nation's policy-making and implementation. The gap in their roles has led to a weakening of their influence, which has subsequently impacted grassroots development. Essentially, this study examines the roles of traditional institutions in the Selected Communities of Osun State, Nigeria, highlighting their significance in resolving conflicts and fostering peace for sustainable development. The work examines obstacles that hinder the effectiveness of these traditional institutions in the study areas. Using a qualitative approach with in-depth interviews and key informant interviews, the study underscores the importance of traditional institutions actively participating in the nation's conflict resolution and peace-making processes. Despite their complexities, traditional positions have become prominent in promoting culture and resolving disputes in the selected cases. The study concludes that traditional institutions and structures should be granted constitutional roles to enhance their capacity and efficiency in managing and resolving local conflicts.

Keywords: Conflicts, Communities, Disputes, Traditional institutions, Traditional Systems

Introduction

Before the establishment of democracy in Nigeria, traditional institutions were present in Nigerian societies through an indirect rule structure that supported Nigeria's traditional administrative development. Hence, the British colonial authority, which established the democratic government in Nigeria, also assigned certain functions to the traditional institutions. By designating them as warrant chiefs and native court judges, the colonial authority acknowledged traditional institutions through the indirect rule system. It is crucial to recognise the substantial contributions traditional leaders made to the development and prosperity of their

communities. As a result, the community chose the leader it believed would perform the best, and a constitutional framework for traditional democracies was established. (Umar, 2022)

Despite the existence of a recognised democratic system, the majority of rural and urban residents believe that traditional institutions control the matters that pertain to their well-being. However, the democratic government and its institutions have not yet reached the majority of the population at the grassroots level, and the traditional authority system remains the primary focus for residents of communities to become aware of and disseminate government policies at the community level (Hill, 2024). Most importantly, the traditional rulers find it simple to carry out the aforementioned duties because the people still hold their various palaces in high regard and reverence. (De Kadt, & Larreguy 2018) Recent studies have highlighted the importance of traditional institutions in the conception and execution of conflict management within their respective domains of influence. The recruitment of subjects for community affairs management, maintaining peace and order within their domain, and coordinating self-help projects based on the aggregated needs of people living there are just a few of the many expected core functions of these institutions. (Osifo, 2017)

The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria is unavoidably silent on the precise functions of traditional rulers within local government. As a result, political appointees who are legally able to appoint and depose traditional leaders will see them as an afterthought. Traditional rulers are only consulted by politicians during election campaigns; they do not influence the formulation, execution, or evaluation of public policy. The usefulness of traditional leaders, particularly in rural areas, was severely hampered by the lack of constitutional rights afforded to them. (Olawoyin, 2023).

Traditional institutions always support government efforts to educate the public on government programs and policies, in addition to their role in community development, so that local citizens feel a sense of involvement in Nigeria's democratic process. As a result, this role has not received enough recognition in Nigeria's democratic system, which has hindered the nation's advancement and growth. (Sokoh, 2018). Nigeria is currently experiencing challenges as a result of several societal issues, such as terrorism, kidnapping, murder, and banditry, which have complicated achieving the anticipated inclusive growth for locals. Many studies have validated the legitimacy and significance of traditional institutions in the sociocultural, economic, and political development of Nigerians, particularly in rural areas. (Eneji & Agri 2020).

Literature Review

Theoretical Review and Framework

One of the key proponents of the structural-functional theory is Robert Merton, along with Herbert Spencer and Talcott Parsons. Social, structural, functional, manifestation, and underlying functions are the main forces that propel the model. The guiding concepts of the

theory include defining the structural components of a system, outlining the functions these components serve, analyzing the impacts of social phenomena on the systems they are part of, and analyzing how new structures emerge. The model adopts a functionalist approach, focusing on society in terms of how its basic elements—such as traditions, practices, norms, and institutions—function. The three pillars of structural functionalism are the preservation of social stability, group functioning, and social evolution. The principal figures include Robert Merton, Talcott Parsons, and Herbert Spencer. (Kalu, 2019).

A society's social structure is composed of several interrelated and interdependent components, including social institutions, social norms, and social ideals. The various roles that each component of the system plays contribute to society's balanced and steady operation. The social structure will adjust as necessary to fulfill societal demands if any part of the structure does. If any section of the structure malfunctions, the entire thing could collapse.

The theory is based on the premise that new bureaucratic principles should consider the commonalities among the traditional, social, and politico-administrative systems of ethnic groups in Africa. It has been claimed that the social and moral obligations that surrounded corporate group representatives may have strengthened the set of rules and laws that regulate them, ensuring the effectiveness of the new bureaucratic institutions. (Hopper & Weyman, 2019). The constant honing relates negatively to the problems with Africa's development, according to the non-Africanist administrative structure. Then, traditional institutions and public administration must be fully integrated, as in the United Kingdom and Spain, to ensure that public institutions in Africa have a working structure that is effective and efficient.

Conceptual Review

The Concept of Traditional Institution and Conflict Resolution for Community Development

The people, both within and outside their domain, hold traditional rulers in high regard as leaders of the people and stewards of the people's culture and traditions. People respect and accept their counsel and opinions on matters, considering their words to be authoritative. The reason for this is that they are respected and cannot be disobeyed, as they are viewed as the link between the people and the gods and their ancestors. (Musa, & Bukar, 2023) Therefore, the government must cooperate and partner with them to resolve any national crises or conflicts that could turn into acts of terrorism in Nigeria. They continue to be a powerful force in the community and, consequently, among their neighbors, safeguarding the peace and harmony of the people in their communities and surroundings, including their close neighbors. (Musa, & Bukar, 2023). To ensure that crises are resolved amicably as soon as they occur, they mediate disagreements and crises that occasionally erupt. Traditional institutions ensured that conflicts were resolved in a manner that effectively managed crises, allowing normal social institutions

and the instruments of control and limitation, referred to as "management," to function. (Lewis, Heathershaw & Megoran, 2018).

Traditional leaders have repeatedly stepped in to address the Niger Delta situation to put an end to the militancy that has been disrupting the country's economic activity, particularly the oil and gas industry. (Odey,2021)

The traditional leaders of Northern Nigeria have been working hard to find a solution to the Boko Haram issue, which has claimed more lives and destroyed more property there than any other disaster. The traditional institutions in Nigeria have also recently been reflecting on the issue facing farmers and herders in the southern part of Nigeria. (Ibraheem, 2015)

Although the traditional leaders' actions may not completely or permanently resolve the disagreements, they are nonetheless effective in mitigating the situation. (Paalo & Issifu, 2022). To maintain the unity of the people and their neighbors, traditional rulers continue to uphold peace and stability not only within their realm but also in Nigeria as a whole and among their near neighbors. (Makinde & Olabode,2019). When El-Rufai, the governor of Kaduna State, stated that "the government will give constitutional tasks to the traditional rulers to oversee the security of people and property in their respective domains," he acknowledged the efforts made by traditional leaders in conflict resolution. (Ali, & Bukar, 2019). This is an effort to stop the ongoing communal fighting and death in several areas of Kaduna.

Role of Traditional Institutions: Managing Inherent Conflict in Local Communities

Traditional leaders serve the economic, social, and political ambitions of their people, which have since become an integral part of our cultural history. Traditional leaders preceded the arrival of British colonization in Nigeria. It is impossible to overstate the value of traditional powers in fostering peace and stability. Traditional authority is valued and relied upon for the advancement of moral ideals in society, in addition to being significant in mobilization efforts. This is partly because these authorities are considered the guardians of the people's customs and traditions, which gives them legitimacy. (Falola, 2021)

Literature affirmed that the public values the part traditional authorities play in handling and resolving conflicts, as well as their leadership skills and adopted approach to common people. It has also been argued that traditional rulers play a significant role in resolving conflict issues between individuals living in their respective domains. (Hilda, & Asiazobor, 2021) Specifically, they ensure that conflicts involving land, communities, and religion are resolved before they escalate into open hostilities that result in human homicide. As a result, the government relies on traditional leaders to maintain social harmony. By making sure that all interpersonal conflicts in each community are resolved or eliminated, and do not develop into ethnic conflicts. Particularly in the Northern region, the diverse structure of Nigerian communities has further solidified support for traditional rulers as crucial partners in ensuring the security of lives and property. (Omitola, Akinrinde, & Omitola, 2021).

Challenges Affecting the Utility of Traditional Institutions of the Selected Communities in Osun State

The progressive decline in the importance of traditional rulers in modern government has been caused by and continues to be caused by several factors. While some of these issues are purposefully created, others are self-inflicted by the old institutions themselves. (Nweke, 2012) The disputes over selection for the Oba ship or chieftaincy institution, in which due process for selection is rooted in the people's customs and traditions, are one of the major challenges affecting the utility of the traditional administration and are self-inflicted. (Emordi & Osiki, 2008) This type of self-inflicted dispute is significantly contributing to the loss of relevance and position in the modern democratic space. The institution should serve as an illustration of the Western democratic process in light of the violent nature of recent elections in Nigeria. When traditional institutions are found to have engaged in such acts of disobedience, their status in society will not improve.

The respect that surrounds traditional institutions/rulers is eroding day by day in Nigeria, which is one of the issues they face. They currently perform errands for politicians, and they are always available to attend events, whether they are important or not. Traditional Rulers, who by custom and tradition are not supposed to be visible everywhere, now parade themselves at government offices in search of various favours. To gain favour with those in power, they take centre stage at political rallies and run for office themselves. Failure to support and obey the politicians frequently results in sanctions and other forms of punishment, such as withholding the funds intended for them, which typically has an impact on the physical development of their communities. (Makinde & Olabode, 2020)

Some of these issues are brought on by traditional institutions, while others are the result of deliberate design. Given this assertion, traditional institutions play a part in Nigeria's democratic relegation process. The Ooni of Ife recently urged cooperation among Nigeria's Obas in an interview conducted on September 16, 2018. His charge was based on his staunch belief that established institutions are capable of providing lasting peace and resolving a variety of problems. He declared that "if there were unity and harmony among our people and the traditional authority in the country, the fight for enviable growth in all sectors of life would be a simple endeavour. (Ogunode, 2021).

The absence of constitutional obligations, a hostile work environment, a lack of official recognition, inadequate government incentives, unreasonably high public expectations, and other unfavourable circumstances also hinder the utility of traditional institutions. (Olorunfemi, & Oloworaran, 2021).

Methodology

The study used a qualitative methodology and a descriptive research design. In Osun State, Nigeria, three specific communities—Ode-Omu, Oke-Ila, and Ifon-Osun—were chosen for the study. 33 people were interviewed using the qualitative research tools. Key Informant Interview (KII) and In-depth Interview (IDI) to gather pertinent data. Key informant interviews are in-depth conversations with individuals who possess in-depth knowledge about the local community. These professionals can give solutions and insight into the nature of challenges. An in-depth interview (IDI) is a strategy for gathering comprehensive information about a subject from a knowledgeable specialist that is open-ended and discovery-oriented. Five traditional council leaders (Kings and high chiefs) from each of the chosen communities participated in the KII sessions, making a total of 15 people. Six participants—three youth association members and three members of trade associations, including market women/men, farmers, and artisans—participated in IDI sessions, totalling 18 participants. The participants were chosen based on their occupation, status, gender, knowledge of traditional institutions, and prior involvement in community development in Nigeria. Thematic content analysis was used to examine the data collected during the fieldwork. This was achieved by organising the data into themes and then comparing the topics before publishing the findings.

Findings and Discussion

The findings of the work were made by its aims and objectives. To guarantee a satisfactory result, the findings were compared to pertinent literature. The relevance of traditional institutions originating from local communities in the southwestern region of Nigeria, in terms of managing inherent conflicts within the democratic dispensation, was emphasized by the findings of this study. Findings from the participants indicated that the nature of conflicts emanating from local communities in Nigeria, especially the southwestern region of the country, is centered mainly on land disputes and political crises among major political parties in the country. These conflicts disrupted the peaceful coexistence enjoyed in the communities, but the swift intervention of traditional institutions prevented the conflicts from escalating into unmanageable situations.

The traditional institutions managed these conflicts through selected traditional high chiefs by inviting the warring parties to the king's palace and employed proactive measures to curb the conflicts between the parties involved: "...Political fight among different factions of political parties and the land dispute is the major crisis during democratic dispensation...Traditional rulers as a father to everybody in the community, quickly intervene by calling all political leaders and the major players in politics to the palace for a peaceful meeting with the king and the high chiefs warning them to control their followers as a proactive measure to save the situation from getting out of control (IDI, Male, 42years Artisan (Bricklayer), Ifon-Osun Community)." This was further illustrated by some of the participants

that the collective efforts of the high chiefs and Baale, in line with the king's support, make the peace process between the aggrieved parties easy and thereby ensure peaceful co-existence in the communities:

The political crisis among the politicians and the boundary disputes between the neighboring communities and marriage disputes are major conflicts in this community... The affected parties are invited to the palace by the high chiefs in charge of disputes and other unacceptable behaviours in the community. The main purpose of the invitation is to broker peace between the people who are fighting and to rise to the occasion to nip the ugly situation in the bud (KII, Male, King, 85 years, **Retired Teacher, Ode-Omu Community**).

Land disputes and political crises among politicians and their followers are the major societal conflicts within this community. The collective efforts and support that the high chiefs and the Baales usually render to the King make the process of settling any disputes among the community dwellers and the aggrieved parties possible, which in turn generates peace and unity among the affected parties (**KII, Male, High Chief (Balogun), 68years, Retired Civil Servant, Ode-Omu Community**).

The responses above indicated that, culturally, traditional councils are known to have the power to adjudicate and preside over matters affecting their people, while also maintaining the boundaries of their territories before they reach court. Undoubtedly, the collective efforts of the leadership of traditional communities, through the King and his Chiefs, have been instrumental in providing quick intervention in cases of conflict and crisis in family, territorial, and political matters. The role of traditional structures is perceived as complementing and helping the democratic society achieve its goal of peace and order, although it has historically been the duty of these institutions.

Similarly, findings indicated that, apart from land disputes and political crises, marriage conflicts among couples are one of the common conflicts that occur in local communities in the southwestern region of Nigeria. This conflict among couples most times resulted in domestic violence with unintended consequences to the family institution and the local communities at large. Importantly, the conflict among couples is mediated by the traditional institution through a constituted committee that investigates and renders a judgment, which is unbiased and satisfactory to the aggrieved parties. This measure employed by the traditional institution has further ameliorated such conflict in the local communities: "...Couples also generated unnecessary disputes and later resulted in domestic violence.... traditional institutions invite the affected parties to the palace for a necessary remedy for the peace to

continue to reign among the community dwellers (**IDI, Female, Women leader (Iyalode), 60years, Trader, Ifon-Osun Community**).”

The findings are further supported in the excerpts of some of the participants that the traditional institution ensures that disgruntled couples are reunited through the constituted committee of High chiefs, and demarcation lines are also set for such parties to douse such conflict from occurring again, which is respected by the concerned couples:

The major conflicts that emerged in this community are mainly land disputes, marriage conflicts, and political crises among the politicians and followers.... traditional institutions settled the land disputes and domestic violence by inviting the parties involved to the palace and the chiefs investigate and the traditional rulers without bias would draw a line of demarcation with the parties involved and they respect the palace decision (**KII, Male, High Chief (Balogun), 67years, Trader, Oke-Ila Community**).

Farm boundary disputes, marriage crises, and political crises are the major problems in this community. Traditional institutions established a committee in the palace to investigate grievances and potential misunderstandings that may arise. The high chiefs in the palace constitute a committee and usually invite the family or individuals who need a remedy or seek justice to the palace for possible reconciliation (**KII, Male, Eesa (Regent), 50 years, Trader, Ifon-Osun Community**).

The assertions above revealed that through the intervention of the high chiefs of traditional administration, marital conflicts, even domestic violence cases, are treated by mediation or by justice, with the end goal of seeking the non-occurrence of such conflicts between the parties involved. This mediation approach by traditional institutions also applies to land disputes in local communities. Although there are structures in the modern system that can manage this, traditional local administration seeks to intervene quickly in such matters before they escalate. The traditional system is a more efficient way of managing and reconciling differences among people based on shared socio-cultural homogeneity, which also lessens the burden on the democratic structure that maintains order and peace.

Findings also confirmed that disputes over farmland and community land boundaries contributed to the conflicts that emerged in local communities in Nigeria. These have pitched families and communities against each other and also degenerated into the loss of lives and properties in the local communities in the southwestern region of the country. The traditional institutions intervened in the crisis due to the sensitive and destructive nature of the conflicts, by inviting the concerned and aggrieved families to the palace and mediated on the conflicts with the hope of ensuring peace and order in the communities: “...Conflicts and disputes

militating against the peaceful atmosphere in this community are farm boundary disputes, and land disputes between families among others...These conflicts were usually settled by the traditional rulers by inviting the parties concerned to the palace to have insight into what happened so as to know how to handle it without bias and to restore peace between them (**KII, Male, High Chief (Sobaloju), 66years, Farmer, Ifon-Osun Community**).” This was illustrated further by some of the participants, who stated that the intervention of the traditional institutions in conflict resolution among the belligerent parties is to keep the community safe from anarchy:

The major disputes and conflicts are boundary disputes among the communities, political thuggery, and land disputes between compounds, among others ...The traditional council’s involvement in managing disputes helps keep the community safe and free from chaos and external threats (**IDI, Male, 43 years, Artisan, Oke-Ila Community**).

Disputes and conflicts are of different dimensions but the major ones in this community are boundary disputes among villages and towns, land disputes, and political crises among the politicians and their followers...traditional institutions settled the crisis and conflicts involving different parties by inviting them to the palace and make a balance between them for peace to reign (**IDI, Male, Youth Association Member, 35years, Farmer, Ifon-Osun**).

The above responses indicate that the equilibrium of the larger society is an aggregation of the order and balance felt in smaller communities, and that the traditional structure has been responsible for maintaining peace against inter-family disputes, inter-community boundary clashes, and external threats. The modern structure cannot handle the complexity associated with some of the historical interactions between communities and families; hence, there is a need for the traditional governance system to complement the democratic system and strategies for maintaining peace and order.

Challenges Affecting the Utility of Traditional Institutions in Community Development in relation to Modern Administration in Nigeria

Findings indicated that traditional institutions’ efforts to contribute to conflict resolution in local communities in the southwest region of the country are hindered by diverse challenges. These challenges ranged from a lack of political power to the lack of political neutrality in traditional institutions and Insecurity. Importantly, the lack of power in the Nigerian constitution has been attributed to the decline in the visible contributions of traditional institutions. This was believed to have hindered the traditional institutions from embarking on some initiatives that could enhance community development in local communities in Nigeria:”

The law that placed the traditional institution under the local government authority is another obstacle for the traditional council to perform its roles effectively. **(KII, Male, High Chief (Otun-Olukotun, 60 years, Surveyor, Ode-Omu Community).**

In other words, the findings indicated that the lack of political neutrality in traditional institutions has further hindered their contributions to conflict and dispute resolution in the southwest region of Nigeria. This is because traditional institutions in partisan politics strain their relationship with political leaders and thereby limit the level of community projects and programmes to the local communities: "...Political affiliation of some high chiefs and even the king is one of the major challenges facing traditional institutions in this community. It affects the relationship with the government in terms of provision from the government official believed that traditional institutions are partisan instead of being neutral politically **(IDI, Female, Women leader, 71years, Trader, Ode-Omu Community).**" This was explained further in the excerpt of a participant:

Most traditional rulers are involved in partisan politics, rather than remaining politically neutral, which can negatively impact their community if their preferred candidate is not in power. The low level of exposure and education among some traditional rulers denied their community a certain level of respect, making it difficult to develop their domain in terms of facilitating community development projects for the betterment of community dwellers **(IDI, Male, Town Development Union Secretary, 53 years, Trader, Oke-Ila Community).**

Discussion of Findings

Findings showed that traditional institutions managed inherent conflicts in local communities concerning the current democratic dispensation through the selection of traditional high chiefs. This was achieved by inviting the warring parties to the king's palace and employing proactive measures to curb the conflicts between the parties involved. This measure, employed by traditional institutions, has further alleviated such conflicts in local communities. This is corroborated in the literature (Osifo, 2017; Darlington, 2020) that traditional rulers play a significant role in settling disputes among people in their respective domains, in terms of land-related disputes, community disputes, and religious crises, before degenerating into unmanageable situations, and are sometimes depended on by the government to promote peace among the community dwellers.

Findings on the challenges affecting the utility of traditional institutions indicated that the absence of functional roles for these institutions in the Nigerian constitution has led to a negative outcome, resulting in most of their struggles to provide solutions to local community problems in the southwest region of Nigeria. This problem has further limited their

performance and effectiveness in conflict resolution, as well as in addressing well-being and social issues, which hinders the development process in local communities in the southwest region of the country. This is in line with the literature (Fatile, 2010; Makinde & Olabode, 2020) that there are factors that contributed to the gradual loss of relevance of traditional rulers in governance of recent which include, self-inflicted problems by the traditional institutions and also the exclusion of the Nigerian 1999 constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria to give specific roles to the traditional rulers and placing them under Local Government which makes the traditional an appendage to political appointees.

Conclusion

Inferencing from the study, traditional institutions have not been accorded meaningful roles in Nigeria's democratic governance; however, their influence on conflict resolution and dispute settlement in recent times has contributed significantly to Nigeria's social, economic, and political development. It is worth noting that the contributions of traditional institutions to conflict resolution and dispute resolution in Nigeria were not made meaningful due largely to limitations in the Nigerian Constitution. The study concluded that traditional Institutions have significantly influenced peaceful coexistence in the southwest region, but their functions and operations are largely limited by the absence of meaningful roles in the Nigerian constitution.

Therefore, the following suggestions could be implemented: The Government at both the federal and state levels should support and reinforce traditional institutions of governance by clearly specifying their roles and modes of operation in the Nigerian Constitution. This is primarily to support their activities in integrating a mode of operation for disputes and conflict resolution into government policies, backed by cogent laws. There is a need for governments at the federal and state levels to ensure routine training and seminar sessions for traditional leaders on capacity building. This is to ensure the integration of traditional leaders in conflict management processes, specifically in mediation and arbitration among warring parties within local communities. This will undoubtedly enhance their skills and expertise in addressing early warning signs of disputes and conflicts and ensure the prevention and resolution of grievances and conflicts in communities across Nigeria.

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